

Unpacking enablers and disablers of transformation: Insights from Central and Eastern Europe as white spots on the global knowledge map

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Abstract:

Calls for transformative change have become central to sustainability research and practice. However, most frameworks and empirical insights on how transformation occurs originate from Western Europe or the Global South. This uneven knowledge production leaves Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) largely invisible in advancing the understanding of transformative change mechanisms. This paper addresses this gap by examining efforts to trigger transformative change at the land-food-energy nexus in Czechia. Drawing on stakeholder analysis and in-depth interviews with key transformative actors, we apply the iceberg model as an analytical framework to unpack the enablers and disablers of transformative change at operational, structural, and narrative levels. While operational and structural enablers and disablers largely mirror those identified in Western European contexts (such as the importance of supportive policies, subsidies, and taxation), those at the narrative level diverge significantly. Historical legacies of state-enforced collectivism in the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic, the path-dependencies of post-1989 political-economic transformation, and the rise of contemporary populism together constrain the legitimacy of transformative change anchored in the principles of solidarity, community, and redistribution. To this end, we argue that globally promoted narratives of transformative change may be normatively powerful yet contextually misaligned. Furthermore, we demonstrate that the CEE experience offers valuable insights into how societies negotiate change under conditions of rigid governance, weak traditions of public participation, pervasive individualism, and transformation fatigue stemming from turbulent socio-economic transitions after 1989.

Key words:

Transformative change, Narratives, Iceberg model, Central and Eastern Europe, Land-food-energy nexus

1 Introduction

The call for transformative change has long resonated across the sustainability research and practice communities, emerging as a central response to the persistent failure to adequately address systemic socio-ecological challenges (Fischer-Kowalski & Rotmans, 2009). In the face of escalating climate change, biodiversity loss, growing social inequities and other interlinked social-ecological crises, transformative change is increasingly understood as a deep, structural reconfiguration of societal systems towards just and sustainable futures (Moore et al., 2014).

Over the past two decades, the notion of transformative change has attracted profound theoretical interest across sustainability science and other research fields, inspiring a proliferation of frameworks and conceptualizations. Some of the many prominent ones include the leverage points for sustainability transformation identifying places in a system for effective interventions (Abson et al., 2017; Meadows, 1999), deliberate social-ecological transformations (Moore et al., 2014), transformative governance (Chaffin et al., 2016; Rusch et al., 2022), transitions (Geels, 2020) and transition management (Loorbach, 2010), pathways approaches (Leach et al., 2010) and collective action in social-ecological systems (McLaughlin & Dietz, 2008) (for a structured review of transformative change frameworks, see Bennett et al. 2025).

In particular, the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment (IPBES TCA) presents a “framework of transformative change for a just and sustainable world”, highlighting the interplay between the underlying causes of unsustainable patterns (disconnection from and domination over nature and people, concentration of power and wealth, and prioritization of short-term, individual and material gains), dimensions of transformative change and key principles guiding it (equity and justice, pluralism and inclusion, respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships, and adaptive learning and action) (IPBES, 2024).

These theoretical framings of transformative change emphasize multi-level interactions, non-linearity, and the importance of agency, institutions, adaptive learning processes, and the necessity to apply a combination of transformative change approaches (Bennett et al., 2025).

Yet, much of the conceptual development and empirical grounding of transformative change has been structured along a North-South axis. In the Global North, the vast majority of transformative change frameworks have originated from the Western European (WE) and North American spaces (e.g., Abson et al., 2017; Geels, 2020; Loorbach, 2010). In the Global South, political ecology and development studies have emphasized decolonial perspectives, power asymmetries, and the importance of local knowledge and justice (e.g., Bennett et al., 2025; Mehta & Harcourt, 2021; Ressorio C. et al., 2024; Vargas Falla et al., 2024).

However, these conceptualizations often reflect their contexts of origin, shaped by the institutional, political, and epistemological environments in which they were developed. This may result in blind spots and conceptual dissonance when applied to other regions. For instance, sustainability and transformation conceptualized from the perspective of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) tend to be misinterpreted, e.g. as mere poverty mitigation strategy (Jehlička, 2021), while CEE perspective can contest some of the framings of participation as a transformative approach emerging from the Global North and South conceptualizations (Head, 2007; Lukatela, 2007; Marchenko, 2016).

This gap is mirrored in emerging literature that critiques the invisibility of the “Global East” in global environmental governance debates. The concept of the Global East (Müller, 2020) challenges the binary nature of recognizing the North and South epistemic spaces, calling attention to the distinct socio-political trajectories of post-socialist countries and their unique institutional and cultural configurations that shape sustainability transformations. Despite growing interest, empirical studies remain scarce, and conceptual engagement is limited.

This observation is emphasised by the notable lack of evidence on how transformative change is understood, perceived, and enacted in the so-called “Global East”, including the CEE region, leading to analytical and empirical gaps in transformative change research. In this respect, in the past decade, there has been an effort in the CEE transformation-related literature to investigate particular aspects of what a more sustainable society could look like, e.g., delving into the possibilities of sustainable revitalisation of urban and agricultural areas (Basova et al., 2019; Farel'nik, 2021; Zielińska-Szczepkowska et al., 2021; Zubala, 2022; Newton et al., 2023), new material development and material circularity including waste management (Babenko et al., 2018; Fořt & Černý, 2020; Duda et al. 2020; Smol et al., 2020; Tomaszewska, 2020; ; Den Boer et al., 2022; Joshi et al., 2024) and energy consumption and its sustainable production (Woźniak & Pactwa, 2019; Czaplicka-Kotas et al., 2020; Żołądek et al., 2022; Jonek-Kowalska & Rupacz, 2023; Rojek et al., 2023; Skiba et al., 2023). However, these papers mostly explore concrete steps towards sustainability that have singular effects; their outcomes are limited to specific sectors or aspects of daily lives. Although exploring these topics can contribute to the creation of more sustainable societies, this research largely does not aim at examining cases of a deep, transformative change that would facilitate a multidimensional transition to a socially and environmentally sustainable way of living.

Indeed, our review showed that only a marginal part of the research on sustainable transformation addresses profound societal changes. Such papers analyse either possibilities of a structural shift or cases of realised interventions towards the implementation of solutions with the potential to reshape the living conditions of impacted populations on multiple levels. In this respect, we identified fewer than 20

articles from four CEE countries (the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland, and Hungary) focusing directly on transformative change, published from the 1990s until the beginning of 2024. Amongst the studies centring deep structural transformations were e.g., a study analysing directions for sustainable post-industrial development of a coal-mining region based on the concept of vitality (Nedvěd & Peřínková, 2017); a study looking into the post-socialist transition as an opportunity for adopting a radically different approach to agriculture (Zagata et al., 2020); a study exploring the emancipatory potential of alternative farmers in regards to food sovereignty and democracy in current authoritarian Hungary (Gonda & Bori, 2023a); or an article theorising institutionalised carpooling system which represents a solution to transport exclusion in the Czech/Polish borderland (Baran & Augustyn, 2021). This literature review thus found that transformative change research and conceptualizations emerging from this region are extremely scarce.

This paper addresses these blind spots by providing empirical evidence on transformative change enablers and disablers from the vastly understudied CEE region. In particular, we focus on transformative change enablers and disablers as related to transformative change in food systems and energy sectors. Both of these sectors represent some of the most fertile terrains for studying transformative change globally, with high potential for future comparison across contexts (Bene & Abdulai, 2024; Crippa et al., 2021; Dorninger et al., 2020; Heyen & Wolff, 2019a). Importantly, both of these sectors intersect with diverse societal interests, ranging from livelihoods, cultural values, and health to infrastructure, regulation, and geopolitics (Gaupp et al., 2021; Queiroz et al., 2021), and are deeply embedded in ecological processes through their impacts on land use, biodiversity, and climate systems (Crippa et al., 2021; Gordon et al., 2017). In this respect, through a qualitative analysis of interviews with Czech transformative actors in the food and energy sectors, we analyse their experience with and reflections of transformative enablers and disablers, highlight the situated, contextual nature of transformation processes, and derive learning points that may diverge from dominant narratives in the sustainability science literature. In doing so, we aim to contribute to a more nuanced, pluralistic, and inclusive understanding of transformative change.

2 Theoretical framework: the iceberg model

The exploration of the enablers and disablers of transformative change in this study was guided by a structured theoretical framework of the “iceberg model”, selected for its well-established nature across domains and its operability.

2.1 The multiple histories of the iceberg metaphor

Across multiple disciplines (incl. anthropology, organizational psychology, and educational theory), the iceberg metaphor has long served as a tool for conceptualizing the relationship between surface-level phenomena and their deeper, often hidden

underpinnings. One of the earliest examples of this metaphor is the "iceberg of culture" model (Hall, 1976), which distinguishes between the visible aspects of culture, such as behaviours, symbols, and customs, and the much larger, invisible dimensions, including values, belief systems, and worldviews. As such, the model facilitates understanding the hidden cultural dynamics that shape human interactions and institutional behaviours. Similarly, in organizational psychology, the "competency iceberg model" (Spencer & Spencer, 1993) contrasts observable knowledge and skills with their underpinning personal attributes such as traits, motives, and self-image. Thus, the competency iceberg model facilitates understanding personal and institutional capabilities for change. In the field of educational psychology, the "learning iceberg" metaphor (Webb et al., 2008; Westenskow et al., 2017) illustrates the hidden emotional and cognitive processes beneath visible learning performance and outcomes.

2.2 The iceberg model in systems thinking

Within the domains of systems thinking and sustainability science, the iceberg metaphor has evolved into a widely applied conceptual tool for engaging with complex systems. Donella Meadows, throughout her lifelong work (later summarized in her posthumously published book *Thinking in Systems*, 2008), emphasized the need to look beyond systems events and symptoms to examine systemic structures and, more critically, the mental models that shape system goals. Consequently, this perspective on systems argues that the most effective leverage for systems change lies not in addressing surface events, but in shifting the paradigms that govern systems.

In the systems thinking understanding, at its core, the iceberg model visualizes systems in four nested levels of increasing depth: events, patterns or trends, systemic structures, and mental models or paradigms. Events constitute the most visible layer, typically manifesting as observable situations and triggering public and policy attention (e.g., floods, protests, price spikes). Beneath events lie patterns, which include recurrent functions and behaviours (e.g., everyday modes of operation within a company). A deeper layer consists of systemic structures, including institutional arrangements, incentive systems, and infrastructural configurations that shape and constrain behaviours. At the base of the iceberg are mental models, i.e., the foundational worldviews, value systems, and assumptions that give rise to and legitimize systemic structures (e.g., deeply held beliefs about development, human-nature relationships, or economic growth).

Building on the developments in systems thinking, the iceberg metaphor has been further operationalized in the context of organizational learning (Senge, 1990), where it has been popularized through the concept of the "learning organization," in which transformation is possible only through seeing beyond immediate problems to the deeper structures and paradigms shaping them. As such, the iceberg became a pedagogical and diagnostic tool to help managers and change agents move from reactive

to generative learning by identifying patterns, structures, and mental models behind observable issues.

Over time, the iceberg model has been refined and widely disseminated across systems thinking literature (Cavana & Maani, 2007; Kim, 1999, 2000; Stroh, 2015). It has also been explicitly linked with the leverage points theoretical framework (McIntyre et al., 2023; Meadows, 2008; Nobles et al., 2022; Traeber-Burdin & Varga, 2022) and applied as the basis for conceptual thinking around deep systems levels (Davelaar, 2021), as well as further theoretical development, e.g. of a theoretical model of the inner transformation (Gray & Manuel-Navarrete, 2021).

2.3 The use of the iceberg model in systems analysis

The practical utility of the iceberg model as a tool for systems analysis has been demonstrated in a wide range of fields. For instance, in health systems, it has been used to map complex causal relationships behind antimicrobial resistance (Matthiessen et al., 2022) and physician shortages (Kelly et al., 2024). In environmental and natural resource management, it has facilitated the identification of local vulnerability dynamics (Matovu et al., 2024), analysis of rebound effects related to sustainability measures (Guzzo et al., 2024), and systems thinking to address natural resource management challenges and complex sustainability issues (Bosch et al., 2007; Nguyen & Bosch, 2013). Furthermore, within the sustainability science community, the iceberg model has been incorporated in practice-oriented frameworks such as Wayfinder (Enfors-Kautsky et al., 2018, 2021), which applies the model to identify deep system drivers and points of intervention.

In this study, the iceberg model serves as a heuristic tool for an in-depth analysis of the identified enablers and disablers of transformative change and offers a critical lens to their discussion.

2.4 Operationalization of the iceberg model

In the light of this theoretical framing, our specific operationalization of the iceberg model is summarized in Figure 1, distinguishing an “operational level” focusing on patterns, a “structural level” focusing on systemic structures shaping behaviour and organizational operation, and “narrative level”, focusing on public discourse legitimizing systemic structures.

Figure 1: Operationalization of the iceberg model as an analytical framework in this study.

3 Methods

The findings presented in this paper are an outcome of the larger transdisciplinary research project TRANSPATH (<https://transpath.eu/>). Specifically, we build on the first phase of the research process that consisted of mapping and analysing the baseline of transformative change. To this end, we undertook two consecutive steps: (1) stakeholder mapping and analysis; and (2) in-depth, semi-structured qualitative interviews with selected transformative actors and their analysis. While the stakeholder mapping and analysis were primarily used for the identification of the transformative actors and their mutual relationships, the interviews were conducted in order to unpack the enablers and disablers for transformative change in Czechia. Data collection and analysis were carried out under the Ethical Codex of the Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences (Regulation No. 1/2017) and were subjected to project-specific Ethical Clearance under reference number VT13/27112023.

3.1 Case study

The land-food-energy nexus in Czechia was selected as the case study scope for several reasons. First, land-based sectors, including food and energy, are crucial for tackling the interconnected challenges of climate change and biodiversity loss, calling for sustainability transformation in both food and energy systems (McElwee et al., 2025). Second, public attention to the land-food-energy nexus has increased substantially over the last couple of years in CEE. The interest in the energy sector is reflected in emerging political discussions on energy security related to geopolitical crises and the mandatory transposition of EU energy legislation (Jirušek, 2023). Furthermore, agriculture and land

use are contentious topics within Czech society as well as in other CEE countries and their associated post-socialist context, with vested interests and lobbying from large agricultural businesses promoting conventional, unsustainable practices, which thus retain the status quo (Bednaříková & Jílková, 2012).

3.2 Stakeholder mapping and analysis

To identify the most relevant stakeholders within the core thematic focus of the TRANSPATH project, we conducted a thorough stakeholder analysis in May and June 2023.

The aim of the stakeholder analysis was to identify and prioritize suitable actors for further engagement in the TRANSPATH project (in-depth interviews and co-production workshops). To do that, we followed the following steps of the stakeholder analysis process outlined by Reed et al. (2009): (1) identifying stakeholders and (2) differentiating between stakeholders and their categorization. First, we created a thorough stakeholder database to identify all potentially relevant stakeholders within the energy-land-food nexus. This was done through in-depth internet research, institutional know-how, and recommendations from other experts in the field. The in-depth interviews that followed stakeholder mapping and analysis (see below) also revealed potential stakeholders, which we subsequently added to the database. This enabled us to integrate both top-down and bottom-up approaches, allowing for reliable and unbiased stakeholder identification as suggested by, among others, Dougill et al. (2006) and Reed et al. (2009).

Secondly, we classified stakeholders according to the scale of their activities (local, national, or regional level, cross-scale), the sector (energy, land, food, or mixed), and the type of organization (public sector, private companies, NGOs, networks, etc.). Finally, we prioritized stakeholders according to the following predefined criteria: (1) stakeholders can be considered as an initiative and/or network connecting multiple initiatives; (2) stakeholders can be considered as transformative, i.e., having a long-term track record of activities that are substantial for transformative change. Application of these criteria resulted in a narrow and compelling list of stakeholders suitable for engagement in the TRANSPATH project.

3.3 In-depth semi-structured interviews with key actors

Following the stakeholder analysis, in the period of August-September 2023, we conducted in-depth semi-structured interviews with key transformative actors representing initiatives and networks with a proven track record in transformative action at the energy-land-food nexus (further referred to as research participants). As many of the actors are simultaneously active in multiple initiatives (as further elaborated in chapter 4.1.1), we identified 16 suitable actors that were invited to the research, out of which 7 participated in the semi-structured interviews. For their general description, see Table 1 in supplementary material. Furthermore, we utilized the principle of thematic

saturation (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016) that ensured the exhaustiveness of the obtained data through the in-depth interviews.

The overarching aim of the in-depth semi-structured interviews was to map out the experience of research participants with pursuing actions oriented towards transformative change (for detailed interview guide, see Supplementary material). We specifically inquired about the concrete examples of actions and external conditions that materialized into achievements of the transformative actors, including lessons learned and their future plans. Intentionally, the interview guide was not designed to explicitly ask about the barriers and obstacles that were encountered during the transformative change-related process, as such questions usually provoke a barrier-oriented thinking and narrative (Norris, 2021). Although it might seem that such an approach would discourage research participants from mentioning any barriers and disabling conditions, the opposite was true. In fact, asking questions about successes stimulated actors to think more in-depth about and to reflect upon the barriers and disablers that were related to their achievements.

In-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted in the Czech language, in-person or online based on the research participant's preference, and with mutual agreement on informed consent. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim, in accordance with the principles outlined in the signed informed consent and the ethical guidelines applicable to the research under the TRANSPATH project.

The transcripts of the in-depth semi-structured interviews were subjected to thematic analysis by using MAXQDA software. The analysis departed from the theoretical framework presented in section 2.4 above and was based on the combination of deductive and inductive coding. First, the data were reduced through deductive coding into categories reflecting the themes emerging from the interview guide. We specifically focused on identifying enablers that reflect the layers of the iceberg model, i.e., the operational, structural, and narrative levels. Also, we extracted information on transformative actors' overarching aims of their transformative efforts as well as on their motivation. During this stage, disablers began to emerge inductively; therefore, we developed new codes and categories to unpack disablers for transformation, also at the operational, structural, and narrative levels. Second, we expand the inductive coding process to unravel more nuanced categories of enablers and disablers at all three levels. Importantly, during the analysis, we did not focus on the quantitative prevalence of the identified themes, but rather evaluated their relevance to the research aims and to the iceberg model. The supporting quotes are presented in Supplementary material.

4 Results

4.1 Who are the transformative actors in the food-energy nexus in Czechia?

4.1.1 Key characteristics of Czech transformative actors

The stakeholder mapping demonstrated a relatively high number (64) of active transformative initiatives and change-makers operating within the land-food-energy nexus. However, a thorough analysis revealed a significant overlap between actors involved in initiatives and networks related to the land-food sector transformation. Furthermore, a vast majority of the identified initiatives were members of wider platforms and networks with a shared, overarching transformative aim. The representatives of these platforms/networks often had a more extensive understanding of the ongoing transformative efforts in Czechia, making them more fitting for our research purposes. In total, we identified 16 actors suitable for engagement in the TRANSPATH project.

Actors engaged in transformative change in the energy sector mainly focus on promoting community energy and renewable sources of energy. That concerns particularly platforms, networks, and think-tanks at the national level that resort to lobbying, but also environmental NGOs, which tend to focus on both national and local scales. The land-food nexus has more variety topic-wise. The majority of initiatives and networks are dedicated to promoting community-supported agriculture (CSA), organic agriculture, and social agriculture on a local scale. However, we also identified wider platforms/associations advocating for a national recognition of the aforementioned sustainable practices alongside local food systems and food supply transformation by lobbying, educational campaigns and programs, and the support of local actors and initiatives.

4.1.2 Motivations and aims of transformative actors

The key motivation and the overarching aim of the transformative initiatives and networks represented by the research participants related to their struggle for equalisation of diverse power imbalances within producer-producer and producer-consumer relationships and beyond. More specifically, the research participants craved for creating and nurturing the notion of complexity of production-consumption relations by problematizing its global and regional aspects and promoting the importance of localisation as the essential path towards sustainability. Finally, as the research participants were mostly representatives of networks of organisations, another important motivation of the transformative actors related to the support of network members in pursuing transformative change.

The research participants operating in the **energy sector** mostly stated that the overarching aim of their initiatives and networks was creating an appropriate legislative environment that would allow for decentralisation of energy production, and for breaking down the dominance of large energy companies through enabling small, often household-level players to enter the energy market. Moreover, the research participants

from the energy sector also aimed at supporting newly emerging energy communities in their efforts to enter the energy markets. This is also related to the fact that the research participants from the energy sector understood individual energy producers and energy communities as key actors for transformation in the current energy sector.

On the other hand, the aims and motivations of research participants representing transformative initiatives and networks in the **land-food sector** were rather broader. Among other things, steering the current state of food production and land utilisation towards higher levels of decentralisation, localisation, and bringing together producers and consumers was a common goal. Specifically, the research participants from the land-food sector aimed at establishing platforms voicing out the needs, activities, and successes of those who are active as producers in the land-food sector, mostly small-scale farmers who utilize land under environmentally conscious regimes. Establishment of platforms was closely related to another aim of altering the major discourse on food production and land utilisation through awareness raising and education of the general public, but also of those enterprises working in the land-food sector.

Across the entire land-food-energy nexus, all these motivations translated into the specific activities carried out by the research participants. For example, a great emphasis was placed on *building communities of change* through *networking and experience sharing* (e.g., best practices) across a wide range of stakeholders. Moreover, the research participants promoted *participation, new forms of democratization, and rethinking hierarchies* as the key principles of transformation towards sustainability. They also supported *cross-scale cooperation of stakeholders* and tended to be active players in the *lobbying* for transformational policy elements at various levels of decision-making. Finally, the research participants were active in the *narrative shifts* by providing stories of success in transformative efforts to cascade them to wider society. Also, they were active in the *communication* of transformative topics.

4.2 Enablers and disablers on the operational level

Enablers at the operational level are related to two categories. The first one refers to the role of the **general public and external support**. To this end, research participants agreed that the *public's trust* towards the aims of the transformative initiative is an essential enabling factor. This is closely related to another enabler of *external support* from the diverse bodies of public administration (e.g., ministries, departments at the municipal level) and from other influential actors, such as other NGOs, well-known public figures, and celebrities. Moreover, the public's trust and the external support are also linked to the enabler of a sense of collectivity, i.e., the feeling of collective belonging to a wider group of like-minded individuals, collectives, and initiatives with similar or complementary aims.

All of these enablers are, to a certain extent, a significant precondition for but also an outcome of the second group of enabling factors of a variety of **personal**

characteristics. Most of the research participants stressed that the essential enabler was *personal qualities* of transformative actors, such as enthusiasm, fearlessness and the willingness to undertake certain risks that were related to their efforts of pursuing transformative change. Importantly, as mentioned by some of the research participants, personal qualities allowed individual transformative actors to engage in the transformative efforts in the long term, even without sufficient reimbursement for their work (in either monetary or non-monetary terms).

Moreover, another important enabler at the side of the transformative actors was the *ability to act flexibly and adaptively if new conditions arose on the go*, such as in cases when the means of ongoing transformative efforts did not prove efficient, and the new ways forward needed to be found. Both enablers, the personal qualities and the ability to act flexibly and adaptively, were closely linked to the profound determination of the research participants for transformative change.

There were only four identified **disablers at the operational level**. The first of them related to an *embeddedness in outdated concepts* that fortified the business-as-usual status quo. According to the research participants, some concepts that were promoted in national policies, such as the requirement for bio certification, no longer reflected the current needs, and instead of providing opportunities for transformation, they were holding it back by creating obstacles for day-to-day operations. This was closely related to the *unavailability of data on transformation*, which discouraged policy and strategy makers from taking up novel ideas and approaches that would break the already-mentioned status quo. Another disabler lies in the *scatteredness and heterogeneity of motivations* that exist among the initiatives, but also among individuals as members of broader networks. As suggested, the actors involved in broader networks often had diverse motivations and interests; therefore, the search for and the formulation of the overarching aims and goals that would be helpful in daily functioning might be hindered by the hardship of representing such heterogeneity. Finally, research participants suggested that *the missing infrastructure (e.g., lack of on-the-ground transformative actors)* across various parts of the value chain disabled day-to-day operations.

4.3 Enablers and disablers on the structural level

Enablers on the structural level generally fell into three categories. The first category reflected on **broader reconfiguration of the policy setting**. For instance, research participants understood national and EU-level *policies and strategies* as an essential precondition for transformation on the structural level. The policies and strategies facilitated bringing novel topics into the socio-political sphere and subsequently adjusting the existing institutional setting accordingly. More specifically, research participants emphasized the necessity of *transposing EU directives* to the national level as vital. Although the EU influence and pressure on the Member states in relation to national policymaking is often perceived negatively, in the energy sector, it was referred

to as vital for kick-starting the transformation of the sector. This substantial EU-driven legislative change allowed small-scale actors who produce energy from renewable resources (mostly in the form of energy communities/ cooperatives) to enter the energy markets and to destabilise the position of the large energy companies, which are dependent on fossil fuels. Similarly, the *ESG reporting obligation* proved to be effective in making companies more sustainable and socially oriented in exchange for financial benefits.

The enablers related to the policy setting were closely linked to another set of enablers related to the **financial mechanisms**. Specifically, the research participants were vocal about the importance of *subsidies and grants* as a precondition for the operation of their initiatives and networks. These often stem from the newly emerging policies and strategies that usually set up conditions for funding schemes. Research participants from the land-food sector tended to use the European Common Agricultural Policy (EU's CAP) as an example. Despite the criticism of the EU's CAP, they acknowledged its role in the legitimization and promotion of organic farming in Czechia from the perspective of policymakers, but also the public. Furthermore, the research participants also emphasized the importance of the related subsidy schemes supporting farmers, motivating their decision to switch their agricultural practices from conventional to organic.

The final category of enabling factors was related to **digitalisation**. The *digitalisation of various administrative processes* was perceived by research participants as providing potential to remove the bureaucratic burden and to ease access to subsidy schemes. Moreover, some of the research participants also mentioned that the policy push related to *digitalisation of data management* in the energy sector was crucial for bringing in principles fundamental to the functioning of community energy (e.g., accumulation, aggregation, flexibility), hence decentralisation of the sector.

Research participants identified numerous **disablers at the structural level** that can be divided into four broad categories. The first category was related to the Czech **institutional setting and functioning of state administration**, but also the governance system in general. For instance, research participants stated the *excessive bureaucracy, lack of supportive legislation, distortion of transformative topics in legislation*, but also generally *top-down oriented legislative/policy making* as major disabling factors for transformation. All of these disablers resulted in a situation in which transformative topics were being framed only through the top-down, narrow-minded perspective, while attempts to put actions into practice were often impeded by overly complicated and time-consuming administrative processes and procedures. Another crucial disabler in this category is related to so-called *sectoralism*, i.e., the situation where responsibility and resources for (not only) transformation processes are fragmented across diverse bodies of public administration that often do not communicate with each other very well.

Finally, according to the research participants, *the rigidity of the Czech governance system promotes a simplistic and non-systematic approach that often fails to address societal and environmental challenges in a holistic way*. Furthermore, it hinders the activities of the non-governmental sector, which often has a substitutive role to the state sector (e.g., it provides certain social services that the state fails to address or provide) and frequently introduces novel approaches. However, regardless of this important role, the state was perceived as neglecting the non-governmental sector through the lack of recognition and consequently the lack of allocated resources.

The second category of disablers included **finance-related aspects of transformation**. While *subsidies* served as an enabling factor for many (see above), they were often perceived as designed in a way that fits large actors better as opposed to the smaller/marginal actors. This was especially visible in the land-food sector, where subsidies oriented on carbon sequestration were seen as generally prioritizing large agricultural businesses that historically contributed to soil degradation the most, while disqualifying smaller, organic farmers whose environmentally friendly practices do not allow them to sequester any additional carbon. Similarly, the current *tax system*, characterized by high taxation of labour and various tax reliefs for larger businesses, was perceived as hindering the transformative potential of the smaller actors. Another finance-related disabler was the *purchasing power* of the inhabitants of the Czech Republic. In general, low real wages and resulting low purchasing power were seen as reducing people's ability to pay for goods and services produced in a sustainable and socially responsible way that are often more expensive than those produced conventionally.

The third category of disablers relates to the **actors who refuse to be active in the transformative efforts**, although their activity would be beneficial for transforming the focal systems. For instance, *missing political personas supportive of transformation* hinder the relevance of the research participants' transformative actions within the broader policymaking process. Furthermore, the research participants emphasized the *lack of multi-actor platforms representing the interests of diverse groups*, which resulted in the marginalization of their voices in policymaking. Research participants also perceived *municipalities as important yet inactive* actors of transformation. Due to the scarcity of finances and capacities, municipalities were perceived to be forced to deal solely with immediate needs, discouraging them from instigating or participating in the transformative processes requiring long-term planning and prioritization of more long-term goals. Finally, the majority of actors in the land-food-energy nexus were seen as not participating in transformative processes – in fact, they were seen as rather discouraged or perceiving transformative change as controversial and not desirable. This implied that the transformative actors felt rather isolated in their efforts. From the perspective of the research participants, this might result from the non-transformative actors perceiving transformation as linked to constantly *increasing bureaucratic requirements* related to

their daily operation. For instance, the obligation of ESG reporting or the push for carbon sequestration in land management tend to be seen as resource-intensive while being understood as a “useless obligation” and as a “waste of energy” for the sake of the EU’s demands.

The last category of disablers focused on diverse **power relations that influence the transformative processes**. Most importantly, the research participants emphasised the skewed producer-producer relations, especially *power imbalances between small and large actors* across scales. These had an effect on who gets to be involved in policy agenda-setting and who benefits or loses from the transformation of the focal sectors. Such imbalances were manifested, for instance, through the *private influence over the governance system* that allowed large actors to impose their own interests on policymakers.

4.4 Enablers and disablers on the narrative level

The **enablers on the narrative level** fell into three categories. The first category referred to the **strengthening narrative power of people seeking an alternative, more sustainable way of life**. For instance, one of the research participants perceived that there is an increasing number of people who are interested in agriculture. In their view, this is partly given by the ongoing *redefinition of organic farming* that strives for the promotion of broader societal values and landscape regeneration. To a certain extent, this is partly driven by the increasing discursive emphasis on a healthy lifestyle, including the diversification of diets through locally and organically produced food. Finally, some of the research participants also perceived an *increased number of people searching for a connection with nature, often via food but also via responsible use of resources (including the energy ones), as vital, especially in terms of spreading the narrative of living in harmony with nature*.

The second category of enablers was related to **changing narratives about life in rural areas**, being closely linked to the previous category. The research participants perceived an increasing trend of *new peasantry movement* in both suburban and rural areas, characterised by the rise of a new generation of young, educated farmers inspired by community supported agriculture (CSA).

Finally, the third category reflected the significantly larger-scale **discursive shifts**. Here, the discursive effect of *global crises* was viewed (especially by research participants from the energy sector) as one of the significant enablers of transformation at the narrative level. For instance, the Covid-19 pandemic created a specific environment that sped up certain transformative processes (for instance, it allowed people to pause and think through their life choices and strengthened people's relationship with nature). Similarly, the energy crisis caused by the war in Ukraine opened previously invisible topics, such as energy self-sufficiency and the need for renewable and community energy. Finally, the research participants identified the enabler of a discourse evolution

due to generational shift, which was seen as crucial, especially in the post-socialist Czech context, leading to the adoption of new perspectives on a range of topics. For instance, the concepts of community and solidarity, previously seen as contentious in the light of the socialist history, were seen as getting new connotations and becoming perceived as an inherent part of more sustainable development rather than a negatively perceived term related to the communist past (as described below).

On the side of **disablers at the narrative level**, two categories emerged. The first one related to the **interest in and communication of transformative topics**. For instance, research participants noted that there were certain *invisible themes* that lay outside of the public and political interest, although they were perceived as fundamental to the social and ecological aspects of societal functioning. On the other hand, the research participants agreed that there was a high (and previously experienced) danger of co-optation of transformative topics in the case that they were picked up by non-transformative actors, who consequently shifted them to less fundamental, thus “safer” narratives. The second category was framed as the **historical path dependence and socio-political features of the society**, hindering transformative narratives from being taken up and scaled. As suggested by the research participants, outside of Czechia, transformation is often promoted via activism and collective solutions. However, in their view, *Czech society strongly prefers to see itself as apolitical*, with high sensitivity towards themes and topics that seem to be somehow political. Furthermore, research participants suggested that Czechs often *seek individual solutions as opposed to collective ones*, which decreases the emphasis on collective action for achieving transformation. Finally, as implied by the previous two categories of disablers, the research participants emphasised the *societal sensitivity to certain topics and terms* as a strong disabler of transformative processes. For instance, the themes related to the current dominant patterns of agricultural production, control of land use and land redistribution, but also to the notions of community, solidarity and cooperatives, are seen as highly contentious in the public debate. All of these topics have generally strong negative connotations due to the historical development of Czechia, and thus disable certain framings and discussions related to transformative processes.

	Operational level	Structural level	Narrative level
Enablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External support • Sense of collectivity • Personal qualities • Ability to act flexibly and adaptably 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies and strategies • Transposing EU directives • ESG reporting obligation • Subsidies and grants • Digitalisation of various administrative processes • Digitalisation of data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Redefinition of organic farming • Emphasis on a healthy lifestyle • An increased number of people searching for a connection with nature • New peasantry movement • Global crises • Discourse evolution due to generational shift
Disablers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embeddedness in outdated concepts • Unavailability of data on transformation • Scatterdness and heterogeneity of motivations • Missing infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive bureaucracy • Lack of supportive legislation • Distortion of transformative topics in legislation • Top-down oriented legislation/policy-making • Sectoralism • The rigidity of the Czech governance system • Subsidies • Tax system • Purchasing power • Missing political personas supportive of transformation • Lack of multi-actor platforms representing the interests of diverse groups • Municipalities as important yet inactive • Increasing bureaucratic requirements • Power imbalances between small and large actors • Private influence over the governance system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invisible themes • Co-optation of transformative topics • Czech society strongly prefers to see itself as apolitical • Seeking individual solutions as opposed to the collective ones • Societal sensitivity to certain topics and terms

5 Discussion

5.1 The application of the theoretical framework

In this study, we employed the iceberg model as an analytical framework for classifying enablers and disablers of transformative change at the land-food-energy nexus, using Czechia as a case study. The iceberg model proved a useful heuristic for engaging with

the systemic nature of the transformative change by providing well-defined and distinguishable categories to classify enablers and disablers. However, it is important to note that in reality, the enablers and disablers of transformative change represent extremely complex phenomena that, in some cases, span multiple categories and can be allocated across multiple iceberg layers at the same time.

Further, the iceberg model is widely used across disciplines (see Chapter 2), and it is recognized by practitioners and researchers, it can be viewed as relatively intuitive and easy to apply compared to more complex frameworks such as D. H. Meadows' (1999) leverage points, which are often difficult to grasp, and their interpretation might provide misleading conclusions. While using well-established leverage points might provide more granularity in terms of intervention logic or feedback dynamics, the iceberg model offers a straightforward and intuitive structure that is widely used beyond academia. Therefore, we believe that the choice of the iceberg model will increase the applicability of our results to practitioners, policymakers, and other actors who are often already acquainted with it.

5.2 Transferability of the research results

The research is based on in-depth qualitative research. Although the results presented in the paper are based on a seemingly limited number of research participants, the thorough stakeholder analysis indicated that the transformative efforts at the land-food-energy nexus are shaped by a relatively small and interconnected set of actors, where most of the research participants are part of multiple initiatives and networks with overlapping activities. Furthermore, we employed the principle of thematic saturation (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015) as a guide for data collection. In this respect, we continued with the interviews until no substantially new categories of enablers or disablers were emerging. This approach ensured that we gained in-depth insight into enablers and disablers encountered by the Czech transformative actors active at the land-food-energy nexus. Moreover, this grounded evidence allows for transferability of the findings that might offer conceptual insights or raise questions relevant for similar actors, initiatives and networks that are related to the transformative change at the land-food-energy nexus in other CEE countries and their post-socialist setting.

5.3 Enablers and barriers to transformative change

The volume of WE research related to identifying enablers and disablers for transformative change within the land-food-energy nexus appears to be significantly larger and more robust than the research coming from the CEE region. Many of the factors discovered in the Czech case study correspond with the evidence from WE countries, particularly enablers and disablers from the operational and structural levels. For instance, the lack of infrastructure allowing for the distribution of locally produced food (Eliasson et al., 2022) and the centralized electricity grid (Kreinin et al., 2024) profoundly hinder food system and energy transformation, respectively, in WE and CEE

countries alike. Additionally, the vast majority of WE research highlights the role of political support, taxation, and subsidies as crucial in enabling or disabling transformative change in both the energy sector and food systems (e.g., Eliasson et al., 2022a; Heyen & Wolff, 2019a; Laes et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2024), which is in line with the presented findings. Furthermore, some research highlights more specific disablers, such as power imbalances between small and large actors and sectoralism prevalent within governance structures (Anderson et al., 2019), or the systematic influence of vested interests, including the fossil-fuel lobby and large food corporations (Kreinin et al., 2024). These disablers are particularly prevalent in agri-food systems characterized by dominant agro-industrial control, related to powerful value chain actors, farmland concentration, and commodification (Williams et al., 2024).

As for the narrative level, only a few enablers arising from the WE region correspond with the Czech case study findings. For example, Heyen & Wolff (2019) highlight the role of global crises as “windows of opportunity” in their case study exploring transformative change in the German energy and agricultural sectors. Also, the role of alternative discourse narratives and framings of food systems was emphasized in many WE case studies, advocating for a radical shift away from the mainstream discourse (Anderson et al., 2019; Eliasson et al., 2022; Kreinin et al., 2024). However, in contrast with the Czech case study, the identified disablers, such as the sensitivity to certain topics and terms rooted in the Czech society as well as its apolitical nature and its preference for individual rather than collective solutions, are missing from the WE literature. Instead, terms such as *community* and *solidarity* are perceived as enablers, specifically related to consumer-producer relationships within WE agri-food systems (Williams et al., 2024).

Moreover, as suggested by Gonda & Bori (2023), Hagedorn (2014), and Kolářová (2020), notions such as *transformation* (or *transition*), *community*, and *solidarity* in Czechia remain deeply entangled with the country’s experience with the pre-1989 socialist regime and post-1989 economic transformation, often carrying apolitical or negative connotations. Below, we unpack how these historically embedded meanings act as strong disablers that pose a critical question: Does sustainability science frame and narrate transformative change in a way that is applicable across contexts?

5.4 Contentious narratives of transformative change

The need to shift dominant narratives around transformative change is increasingly recognized as a critical precondition for sustainability transformation. As Linnér & Wibeck (2021a) and Schrandt et al. (2024) argue, narratives shape the ways societies understand problems and imagine solutions, thereby being powerful in reconfiguring social norms and policy goals towards a more sustainable future. Hence, sustainability science and its call for transformative change do more than diagnose which narratives require change (Fazey et al., 2018; Marciniak et al., 2024). It actively constructs and promotes new *counternarratives* intended to replace the existing ones. Such emerging

counternarratives are commonly centred around reduced consumption and production, a recognition of interdependence between society and nature, the cultivation of solidarity- and justice-oriented economic systems associated with a profound redistribution system, and participatory forms of governance that promote accountability (Gosnell et al., 2025; Riedy, 2020).

However, our findings reveal that many of these normatively powerful counternarratives are contentious and encounter resistance in Czechia and, by extension, in much of the CEE region. The *societal sensitivity to certain topics and terms* functions as a distinct disabler that hinders the success of the counternarratives promoted by sustainability science. While the backlash of the counternarratives exists elsewhere (e.g., Anderson et al., 2019; de Koning, 2024; Eliasson et al., 2022; Schrandt et al., 2024), in Czechia it is amplified by the historical legacies of the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic (CSSR, 1948-1989) and the post-1989 transformation from state control to a neoliberal economy. In this respect, there are three key path-dependencies that illustrate this pattern and offer learning points for sustainability and transformative change scholars beyond the CEE context.

First, for much of the Czech public and the mainstream debate, the terms and concepts such as “community”, “solidarity”, “collective action”, or “redistribution” remain burdened with associations of state-imposed collectivism under the CSSR. Consequently, these terms and concepts remain tainted by their authoritarian connotations and are either avoided or stripped of their normative depth (Gonda & Bori, 2023b; Hagedorn, 2014). This is well demonstrated by the testimonies of our research participants, as well as by Kolářová (2020). In her research on the Czech permaculture movement, she demonstrates that the practices elsewhere carry politically transformative meanings (e.g., Roux-Rosier et al., 2018) that are here reframed as expressions of individual self-reliance, leisure, and personal spirituality, rather than collective politics (Kolářová, 2020).

Second, the very term “transformation” carries a powerful load in the Czech context. The post-1989 political and socio-economic transformation (further referred to as post-socialist transformation) is commonly seen as definitive – a path from authoritarianism to freedom, from planned economy to market capitalism that reached its destination. As such, the “transformation” is frequently perceived as something already accomplished, as a win of the good and natural (i.e., capitalism) over the bad and unnatural (i.e., communism) (Babička, 2022; Prushankin, 2023; Weiner, 2010) and not as an ongoing, future-oriented process as suggested by the sustainability science (Gurung et al., 2025; Janita et al., 2025). As a result, contemporary calls for sustainability transformation, emphasizing redistribution, solidarity with other human beings and the nature, modest lifestyles, consumption reduction and sometimes even for slower (or none) economic growth, often appears to be regressive and directive (Durdovic et al., 2025), while evoking

sentiments of scarcity and state control (Krapfl, pp. 80-103, 2019; Prushankin, 2023). Moreover, although initially the post-socialist transformation was led by the promise of “life in the wealth” and “opportunities for all”, the opposite was true – new social stratification has emerged, marked by the new forms of precarity and loss of social security for many (Hruška & Píša, 2019; Illner, 1996). Therefore, the calls for transformative change might provoke anxieties about uncertainty, loss and insecurity, especially among those who Prokop et al. (2019) call the “endangered class” and “languishing class” (together making up 40% of the Czech population).

Third, and complicating matters even further, in Czechia and the CEE region in general, the populist, illiberal, and far-right movements are gaining part of their momentum through backlash against the European Union and its pro-transformative policies, such as the European Green Deal (Kevicky, 2023; Nagy et al., 2025; Pittnerová & Kopeček, 2025; Žuk & Žuk, 2024). They frequently reframe sustainability-oriented counternarratives as “ideological imports [from the West]”, “dictate from Brussels”, “green madness” or “new communism” (Durdovic et al., 2025). Such rhetoric resonates strongly among those with lived experience of both the socialist and post-1989 eras. Consequently, counternarratives advocating for solidarity and redistribution for achieving sustainability transformation often fall on barren ground. Instead, they may actually fortify dominant narratives of neoliberal progress and anti-solidaristic individualism.

Together, these dynamics illustrate how the legitimacy of counternarratives and the discursive space for imagining transformative change can be constrained by historical and political burdens and path dependencies. More importantly, our findings show that WE-driven sustainability science might promote counternarratives that are normatively robust but contextually misaligned in post-socialist societies. Therefore, we question whether the transformative change in Czechia and similar contexts should be framed by the same narrative templates as promoted by sustainability science, which are mostly built on the experience from the North-South epistemic axis (e.g., Gosnell et al., 2025; Linnér & Wibeck, 2021; Schrandt et al., 2024).

Therefore, building on the work of Müller (2020) and Jehlička (2021), we suggest that de-centring the North-South dichotomy in sustainability science is urgently needed to create a space for a more pluralistic and context-sensitive understanding of transformative change (Fazey et al., 2018; Lahsen & Turnhout, 2021). To this end, recognizing the Global East (with CEE as part of it) as an epistemic region, rather than a transitional space between the Global North and South, can uncover critical blind spots on the global map of knowledge production (Sovová et al., 2025; Starnawski & Warren, 2023; Stoker et al., 2025). This matters at least for three intertwined reasons. First, as shown above, sustainability science necessarily does not have to promote counternarratives for transformative change that are universal to all contexts (even if

modified and adapted). Second, taking into consideration the narrative dynamics of Global East can stimulate further thinking of how to use the existing dominant narratives to the advantage of transformative change. Third, it allows for theorizing new, empirically grounded counternarratives of transformative change that might be applicable beyond the Global East, especially by other transformation-fatigued societies worldwide.

6 Conclusion

This paper advances debates on transformative change at the land-food-energy nexus by building on situated evidence from Czechia. To this end, we utilize the iceberg model to construct an in-depth understanding of the enabling and disabling factors of the transformative change, focusing on operational, structural, and narrative levels. Our results show that the enablers and disablers at operational and structural levels echo the Western European experience (e.g., in terms of the role of infrastructure, subsidies, taxation, sectoralism, and power asymmetries between small and large players). However, the narrative level diverges sharply – while the sustainability science promotes concepts such as community and solidarity as key to the transformative change, the evidence from Czechia shows that these might be extremely triggering and viewed as illegitimate in the post-socialist contexts.

To this end, we highlight the need for critical examination of the narrative templates of transformative change promoted by sustainability science, which are often based on theoretical framings originating mainly from the North-South axis of knowledge production. Therefore, we invite other scholars from the broader Central and Eastern European region (and others who identify themselves as coming from the Global East) to claim their epistemic space and to unpack how their path-dependencies and situated experiences of post-socialist transformation play out in broader transformative change efforts. Only then might the universalized assumptions of sustainability science be scrutinized, allowing for more pluralistic transformation pathways.

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References

- Abson, D. J., Fischer, J., Leventon, J., Newig, J., Schomerus, T., Vilsmaier, U., von Wehrden, H., Abernethy, P., Ives, C. D., Jager, N. W., & Lang, D. J. (2017). Leverage points for sustainability transformation. *Ambio*, 46(1), 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0800-y>
- Anderson, C. R., Bruil, J., Chappell, M. J., Kiss, C., & Pimbert, M. P. (2019). From Transition to Domains of Transformation: Getting to Sustainable and Just Food Systems through Agroecology. *Sustainability*, 11(19), Article 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11195272>
- Babenko, M., Estokova, A., Savytskyi, M., & Unčák, S. (2018). Study of Thermal Properties of Lightweight Insulation Made of Flax Straw. *Slovak Journal of Civil Engineering*, 26(2), 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.2478/sjce-2018-0008>
- Babička, M. (2022). “The future is in your hands”: Temporality and the neoliberal self in the Czech voucher privatization. *Journal of Contemporary Central and Eastern Europe*, 30(1), 83–99. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25739638.2022.2044616>
- Baran, M., & Augustyn, D. J. (2021). The Evaluation of Transport Exclusion in the Peripheral Cross-Border Areas of Central Europe in the Context of Applicability of Information-Based Carpooling. *Sustainability*, 13(6), 3440. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063440>
- Basova, S., Sopiřova, A., & Kristianova, K. (2019). Potential of Recycling Urban Territories. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 471, 092053. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/471/9/092053>

- Bednaříková, Z., & Jílková, J. (2012). Why is the agricultural lobby in the European Union member states so effective? *E a M: Ekonomie a Management*, 15, 26–37.
- Bene, C., & Abdulai, A.-R. (2024). Navigating the politics and processes of food systems transformation: Guidance from a holistic framework. In *FRONTIERS IN SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS* (Vol. 8). FRONTIERS MEDIA SA. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399024>
- Bennett, E., Biggs, R., Calderón Contreras, R., Golden Kroner, R., Vianna Mansur, A., Woroniecki, S., Acar, S., Aksoy, Z., Alpizar, F., Lam, D., Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Linnér, B.-O., Mehta, L., Campos, C. M., Nishi, M., Roskruge, N., Richardson, M., Sabinot, C., Simão Seixas, C., ... Garibaldi, L. A. (2025). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Chapter 3. How transformative change occurs*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268235>
- Bosch, O., Maani, K., & Smith, C. (2007). Systems thinking – Language of complexity for scientists and managers. In S. Harrison, A. Bosch, & J. Herbohn (Eds.), *Improving the triple bottom line returns from small-scale forestry* (pp. 57–66). The University of Queensland.
- Cavana, R. Y., & Maani, K. E. (2007). *Systems Thinking, System Dynamics: Managing Change and Complexity*. Pearson Education Canada.
- Chaffin, B. C., Garmestani, A. S., Gunderson, L. H., Benson, M. H., Angeler, D. G., Arnold, C. A. (Tony), Cosens, B., Craig, R. K., Ruhl, J. B., & Allen, C. R. (2016). Transformative Environmental Governance. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 41(1), 399–423. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085817>
- Crippa, M., Solazzo, E., Guizzardi, D., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Tubiello, F. N., & Leip, A. (2021). Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nature Food*, 2(3), 198–209. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>
- Czaplicka-Kotas, A., Kulczycka, J., & Iwaszczuk, N. (2020). Energy Clusters as a New Urban Symbiosis Concept for Increasing Renewable Energy Production—A Case Study of Zakopane City. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5634. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12145634>
- Davelaar, D. (2021). Transformation for sustainability: A deep leverage points approach. *Sustainability Science*, 16(3), 727–747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00872-0>
- de Koning, S. (2024). Landscape discourses and rural transformations: Insights from the Dutch Dune and Flower Bulb Region. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 41(4), 1431–1448. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-024-10559-2>
- Den Boer, E., Banaszkiwicz, K., Den Boer, J., & Pasiiecznik, I. (2022). Energy Recovery from Waste—Closing the Municipal Loop. *Energies*, 15(3), 1246. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15031246>

- Dorninger, C., Abson, D. J., Apetrei, C. I., Derwort, P., Ives, C. D., Klaniecki, K., Lam, D. P. M., Langsenlehner, M., Riechers, M., Spittler, N., & Von Wehrden, H. (2020). Leverage points for sustainability transformation: A review on interventions in food and energy systems. *Ecological Economics*, *171*, 106570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.106570>
- Dougill, A. J., Fraser, E. D. G., Holden, J., Hubacek, K., Prell, C., Reed, M. S., Stagl, S., & Stringer, L. C. (2006). Learning from doing participatory rural research: Lessons from the Peak District National Park. *JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS*, *57*(2), 259–275. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9552.2006.00051.x>
- Durdovic, M., Kolářová, M., & Čermák, D. (2025). Public resistance to climate policy amid energy crisis and populism: The case of the European Green Deal in the Czech Republic. *Energy Research & Social Science*, *123*, 104033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104033>
- Eliasson, K., Wiréhn, L., Naset, T.-S., & Linnér, B.-O. (2022). Transformations towards sustainable food systems: Contrasting Swedish practitioner perspectives with the European Commission's Farm to Fork Strategy. *Sustainability Science*, *17*(6), 2411–2425. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01174-3>
- Enfors-Kautsky, E., Järnberg, L., Quinlan, A., & Ryan, P. (2018). *Wayfinder A resilience guide for navigating towards sustainable futures*. GRAID Programme, Stockholm Resilience Center, Stockholm, Sweden. <https://wayfinder.earth/>
- Enfors-Kautsky, E., Järnberg, L., Quinlan, A., & Ryan, P. (2021). Wayfinder: A new generation of resilience practice. *Ecology and Society*, *26*(2). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12176-260239>
- Farelnik, E. (2021). Revitalisation as a tool for the development of slow city (Cittaslow). *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, *9*(2), 169–185. [https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.9.2\(11\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.9.2(11))
- Fazey, I., Moug, P., Allen, S., Beckmann, K., Blackwood, D., Bonaventura, M., Burnett, K., Danson, M., Falconer, R., Gagnon, A. S., Harkness, R., Hodgson, A., Holm, L., Irvine, K. N., Low, R., Lyon, C., Moss, A., Moran, C., Naylor, L., ... Wolstenholme, R. (2018). Transformation in a changing climate: A research agenda. *Climate and Development*, *10*(3), 197–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2017.1301864>
- Fischer-Kowalski, M., & Rotmans, J. (2009). Conceptualizing, Observing, and Influencing Social-Ecological Transitions. *Ecology and Society*, *14*(2), 3.
- Fořt, J., & Černý, R. (2020). Transition to circular economy in the construction industry: Environmental aspects of waste brick recycling scenarios. *Waste Management*, *118*, 510–520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.09.004>
- Gaupp, F., Laderchi, C. R., Lotze-Campen, H., DeClerck, F., Bodirsky, B. L., Lowder, S., Popp, A., Kanbur, R., Edenhofer, O., Nugent, R., Fanzo, J., Dietz, S., Nordhagen, S., & Fan, S. (2021). Food system development pathways for healthy, nature-positive and inclusive food systems. In *NATURE FOOD* (Vol. 2, Issue 12, pp. 928–934). NATURE PORTFOLIO. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00421-7>

- Geels, F. W. (2020). Micro-foundations of the multi-level perspective on socio-technical transitions: Developing a multi-dimensional model of agency through crossovers between social constructivism, evolutionary economics and neo-institutional theory. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 152(December 2019), 119894. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119894>
- Gonda, N., & Bori, P. J. (2023a). Rural politics in undemocratic times: Exploring the emancipatory potential of small rural initiatives in authoritarian Hungary. *Geoforum*, 143, 103766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2023.103766>
- Gonda, N., & Bori, P. J. (2023b). Rural politics in undemocratic times: Exploring the emancipatory potential of small rural initiatives in authoritarian Hungary. *Geoforum*, 143, 103766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2023.103766>
- Gordon, L. J., Bignet, V., Crona, B., Henriksson, P. J. G., Van Holt, T., Jonell, M., Lindahl, T., Troell, M., Barthel, S., Deutsch, L., Folke, C., Haider, L. J., Rockström, J., & Queiroz, C. (2017). Rewiring food systems to enhance human health and biosphere stewardship. *Environmental Research Letters*, 12(10). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aa81dc>
- Gosnell, H., Reyes García, V., Zinngrebe, Y., Almeida Magris, R., Benessaiah, K., Bonilla-Moheno, M., Chandipo, R., Claudet, J., Gemmill-Herren, B., Goldstein, B., Huntjens, P., Ifejika Speranza, C., Nakao, F., Pandit, R., Bosch Pereira, L., Raab, K., Soares, T., Tittonell, P., Guo, X., ... Garibaldi, L. (2025). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Chapter 5. Realizing a sustainable world for nature and people: transformative strategies, actions and roles for all*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15120548>
- Gray, K., & Manuel-Navarrete, D. (2021). Leveraging inner sustainability through cross-cultural learning: Evidence from a Quichua field school in Ecuador. *Sustainability Science*, 16(5), 1459–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00980-5>
- Gurung, J., Leventon, J., Wickson, F., Dabezies, J., Olemako, T., Penca, J., Rajvanshi, A., Roseline, R., Turnhout, E., Yoshida, Y., Kahrić, A., Naggea, J., & Renaud, A. (2025). *IPBES Transformative Change Assessment: Chapter 1. Transformative change and a sustainable world*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16310122>
- Guzzo, D., Walrave, B., Videira, N., Oliveira, I. C., & Pigosso, D. C. A. (2024). Towards a systemic view on rebound effects: Modelling the feedback loops of rebound mechanisms. *Ecological Economics*, 217, 108050. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.108050>
- Hagedorn, K. (2014). Post-Socialist Farmers' Cooperatives in Central and Eastern Europe. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, 85(4), 555–577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12051>
- Hall, E. T. (Edward T. (with Internet Archive). (1976). *Beyond culture*. Garden City, N.Y. : Anchor Press. http://archive.org/details/beyondculture0000hall_t6d8

- Hartvigsen, M. (2014). Land reform and land fragmentation in Central and Eastern Europe. *Land Use Policy*, 36, 330–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.08.016>
- Head, B. W. (2007). Community engagement: Participation on whose terms? *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 42(3), 441–454. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10361140701513570>
- Heyen, D. A., & Wolff, F. (2019a). Drivers and barriers of sustainability transformations: A comparison of the “Energiewende” and the attempted transformation to organic agriculture in Germany. *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 28(1), 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.28.S1.9>
- Heyen, D. A., & Wolff, F. (2019b). Drivers and barriers of sustainability transformations: A comparison of the “Energiewende” and the attempted transformation to organic agriculture in Germany. *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 28(1), 226–232. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.28.S1.9>
- Hruška, V., & Píša, J. (2019). Winning and losing rural localities of the post-socialist economic restructuring: Case study of Czechia. *Hungarian Geographical Bulletin*, 68(4), 373–389. <https://doi.org/10.15201/hungeobull.68.4.4>
- Illner, M. (1996). Post-Communist Transformation Revisited. *Sociologický Časopis / Czech Sociological Review*, 32(2), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.13060/00380288.1996.32.12.06>
- IPBES. (2024). *Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*. IPBES Secretariat.
- Jehlička, P. (2021). Eastern Europe and the geography of knowledge production: The case of the invisible gardener. *Progress in Human Geography*, 45(5), 1218–1236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132520987305>
- Jirušek, M. (2023). The Czech EU Presidency: Strengthening Energy Security Amidst the Crisis. *Czech Journal of International Relations*, 58(1), 147–157. <https://doi.org/10.32422/mv-cjir.702>
- Jonek-Kowalska, I., & Rupacz, S. (2023). The Innovative Nature of Selected Polish Companies in the Energy Sector Compared to the Use of Renewable Energy Sources from a Financial and an Investor’s Perspective. *Resources*, 12(12), 147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources12120147>
- Joshi, N., Grewal, J., Drewniak, L., & Pranaw, K. (2024). Bioprospecting CAZymes repertoire of *Aspergillus fumigatus* for eco-friendly value-added transformations of agro-forest biomass. *Biotechnology for Biofuels and Bioproducts*, 17(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13068-023-02453-6>

- Kevicky, D. (2023). 'We Will Protect Our Countryside without a Green Deal': The Populist Radical Right and the Environment in Czechia and Slovakia. *European Journal of Geography*, 14(2), 32–43. <https://doi.org/10.48088/ejg.d.kev.14.2.032.043>
- Kim, D. H. (1999). *Introduction to Systems Thinking*. Pegasus Communications.
- Kim, D. H. (2000). *Systems Thinking Tools: A User's Reference Guide*. Pegasus Communications. <https://docslib.org/doc/10635905/systems-thinking-tools-a-users-reference-guide-by-daniel-h>
- Kolářová, M. (2020). Climate Change and the Transition Movement in Eastern Europe: The Case of Czech Permaculture. *Sociologický Časopis / Czech Sociological Review*, 56(3), 363–386.
- Krapfl, J. (2019). Czechoslovakia's year of decision: From the socialist revolution of 1989 to the 'real' revolution of 1990. In *From Revolution to Uncertainty*. Routledge.
- Kreinin, H., Fuchs, D., Mamut, P., Hirth, S., & Lange, S. (2024). Transforming provisioning systems to enable 1.5° lifestyles in Europe? Expert and stakeholder views on overcoming structural barriers. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 20(1), 2372120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2024.2372120>
- Laes, E., Valkering, P., & De Weerd, Y. (2019). Diagnosing Barriers and Enablers for the Flemish Energy Transition. *Sustainability*, 11(20), Article 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205558>
- Lahsen, M., & Turnhout, E. (2021). How norms, needs, and power in science obstruct transformations towards sustainability. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(2), 025008. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abdcd0>
- Leach, M., Scoones, I., & Stirling, A. (2010). Governing epidemics in an age of complexity: Narratives, politics and pathways to sustainability. *Global Environmental Change, Governance, Complexity and Resilience*, 20(3), 369–377. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2009.11.008>
- Linnér, B.-O., & Wibeck, V. (2021). Drivers of sustainability transformations: Leverage points, contexts and conjunctures. *Sustainability Science*, 16(3), 889–900. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00957-4>
- Loorbach, D. (2010). Transition Management for Sustainable Development: A Prescriptive, Complexity-Based Governance Framework. *Governance*, 23(1), 161–183. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0491.2009.01471.x>
- Lukatela, A. (2007). The Importance of Trust-Building in Transition: A Look at Social Capital and Democratic Action in Eastern Europe. *Canadian Slavonic Papers*, 49(1–2), 49–68. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00085006.2007.11092430>
- Marchenko, A. (2016). Civic activities in Eastern Europe: Links with democratic political culture. *East European Politics*, 32(1), 12–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21599165.2015.1130698>
- Marciniak, G., Urbach, D., Schneider, F., Krug, C., Bremond, A. de, Stafford-Smith, M., Selomane, O., Fenn, R., Chong, N., & Paillard, S. (2024). Leveraging capacity for transformative sustainability science: A theory of change from the Future Earth

- Pathways Initiative. *Global Sustainability*, 7, e21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sus.2024.19>
- Matovu, B., Lukumbagire, I., Mwabvu, B., Manianga, A., Alkoyak-Yildiz, M., S., N., Jabbi, B., & Etta, L. A. (2024). Co-designing transformative ocean sustainability narratives to address complex human-environmental challenges facing coastal fisherwomen: An evidence-based study. *Environmental Challenges*, 15, 100923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2024.100923>
- McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Harmáčková, Z., Hayman, D. T. S., Herrero, M., Kumar, R., Ley, D., Mangalagiu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Pengue, W. A., Prist, P. R., Ricketts, T. H., Rounsevell, M. D. A., ... Obura, D. (2025). *IPBES Nexus Assessment: Summary for Policymakers*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15673657>
- McIntyre, D. G., Cloutis, G. A., & McCarthy, D. (2023). Indigenous trans-systemics: Changing the volume on systems. *Sustainability Science*, 18(4), 1961–1975. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01330-3>
- McLaughlin, P., & Dietz, T. (2008). Structure, agency and environment: Toward an integrated perspective on vulnerability. *Global Environmental Change*, 18(1), 99–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2007.05.003>
- Meadows, D. (2008). *Thinking in Systems*. Chelsea Green Publishing.
- Meadows, D. H. (1999). *Leverage points: Places to Intervene in a system*. The Sustainability Institute.
- Mehta, L., & Harcourt, W. (2021). Beyond limits and scarcity: Feminist and decolonial contributions to degrowth. *Political Geography*, 89, 102411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2021.102411>
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. J. (2015). *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Moore, M.-L., Tjornbo, O., Enfors, E., Knapp, C., Hodbod, J., Baggio, J. A., Norström, A., Olsson, P., & Biggs, D. (2014). Studying the complexity of change: Toward an analytical framework for understanding deliberate social-ecological transformations. *Ecology and Society*, 19(4), art54. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-06966-190454>
- Müller, M. (2020). In Search of the Global East: Thinking between North and South. *Geopolitics*, 25(3), 734–755. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2018.1477757>
- Nagy, G., Heiner, S. Á., & Kovács, Z. (2025). Exploring the Presence and Absence of Academic Discourse on Public Participation in the European Green Deal: A Central and Eastern European Perspective. *Societies*, 15(3), 49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc15030049>
- Nedvěd, M., & Peřinková, M. (2017). *THE CITY OF OSTRAVA (CZECH REPUBLIC): A SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT BASED ON VITALITY*. 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.2495/SC170021>

- Newton, R. A., Pidlisnyuk, V., Wildová, E., Nováková, L., & Trögl, J. (2023). State of Brownfields in the Northern Bohemia, Saxony and Lower Silesian Regions and Prospects for Regeneration by Utilization of the Phytotechnology with the Second Generation Crops. *Land*, 12(2), 354. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land12020354>
- Nguyen, N. C., & Bosch, O. J. H. (2013). A Systems Thinking Approach to identify Leverage Points for Sustainability: A Case Study in the Cat Ba Biosphere Reserve, Vietnam. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 30(2), 104–115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2145>
- Nobles, J., Wheeler, J., Dunleavy-Harris, K., Holmes, R., Inman-Ward, A., Potts, A., Hall, J., Redwood, S., Jago, R., & Foster, C. (2022). Ripple effects mapping: Capturing the wider impacts of systems change efforts in public health. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 22(1), 72. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-022-01570-4>
- Norris, C. J. (2021). The negativity bias, revisited: Evidence from neuroscience measures and an individual differences approach. *Social Neuroscience*, 16(1), 68–82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17470919.2019.1696225>
- Pittnerová, Š., & Kopeček, L. (2025). No to the ‘mad’ Green Deal, yes to ‘quality’ Czech food: How the far-right populist Freedom and Direct Democracy messages on environmental issues. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 0(0), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14782804.2025.2525145>
- Prokop, D., Tabery, P., Buchtík, M., Dvořák, Tomáš., & Pilnáček, Matouš. (with Šibík, J.). (2019). *Rozdělení svobodou: Česká společnost po 30 letech*. Radioservis, a.s.
- Prushankin, K. (2023). Neoliberalism or Else: The Discursive Foundations of Neoliberal Populism in the Czech Republic. *Czech Journal of International Relations*, 58(2), 43–71. <https://doi.org/10.32422/mv-cjir.431>
- Queiroz, C., Norström, A. V., Downing, A., Harmáčková, Z. V., De Coning, C., Adams, V., Bakarr, M., Baedeker, T., Chitate, A., Gaffney, O., Gordon, L., Hainzelin, É., Howlett, D., Krampe, F., Loboguerrero, A. M., Nel, D., Okollet, C., Rebermark, M., Rockström, J., ... Matthews, N. (2021). Investment in resilient food systems in the most vulnerable and fragile regions is critical. *Nature Food*, 2(8), 546–551. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00345-2>
- Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C. H., & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who’s in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(5), 1933–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>
- Ressioire C., A., Ludwig, D., & El-Hani, C. (2024). The conceptual potential of ‘more-than-human care’: A reflection with an artisanal fishing village in Brazil. *Geo: Geography and Environment*, 11(2), e00159. <https://doi.org/10.1002/geo2.159>
- Riedy, C. (2020). Discourse coalitions for sustainability transformations: Common ground and conflict beyond neoliberalism. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Open Issue 2020 Part A: Technology Innovations and*

- Environmental Sustainability in the Anthropocene*, 45, 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.09.014>
- Rojek, I., Mroziński, A., Kotlarz, P., Macko, M., & Mikołajewski, D. (2023). AI-Based Computational Model in Sustainable Transformation of Energy Markets. *Energies*, 16(24), 8059. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16248059>
- Rusch, G. M., Bartlett, J., Kyrkjeeide, M. O., Lein, U., Nordén, J., Sandvik, H., & Stokland, H. (2022). A joint climate and nature cure: A transformative change perspective. *Ambio*, 51(6), 1459–1473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01679-8>
- Schrandt, N., Wittmayer, J. M., & Metze, T. (2024). Unravelling the discursive dynamics of counternarratives in the Dutch energy transition. *The Extractive Industries and Society*, 20, 101546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exis.2024.101546>
- Senge, P. (1990). *The fifth discipline: The art and practice of the learning organization* (Vol. 29). New York: Doubleday/Currency. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/hrm.3930290308>
- Skiba, M., Mrówczyńska, M., Sztubecka, M., Maciejko, A., & Rzeszowska, N. (2023). The European Union’s Energy Policy Efforts Regarding Emission Reduction in Cities—A Method Proposal. *Energies*, 16(17), 6123. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16176123>
- Smol, M., Duda, J., Czaplicka-Kotas, A., & Szotłowska, D. (2020). Transformation towards Circular Economy (CE) in Municipal Waste Management System: Model Solutions for Poland. *Sustainability*, 12(11), 4561. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114561>
- Sovová, L., Cima, O., Jehlička, P., Pungas, L., Sattler, M., Smith, T. S. J., Decker, A., Johanisova, N., Kovanen, S., North, P., & Collective, P. (2025). On Babushkas and Postcapitalism: Theorising Diverse Economies from the Global East. *Antipode*, 57(6), 2484–2507. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.70034>
- Spencer, L. M., & Spencer, S. M. (1993). Competence at Work. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 5(4), 391–395. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrdq.3920050411>
- Starnawski, M., & Warren, S. (2023). Central and Eastern Europe in Academic Internationalization: Peripherality, Neoliberalism, and Knowledge Production. *Studia Litteraria et Historica*, (12). <https://doi.org/10.11649/slh.3184>
- Stoker, A., Masná, E., Kvasničková, K., & Novotný, J. (2025). Uncomfortable geographies of research ethics: A view from the academic semi-periphery. *Geoforum*, 166, 104426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2025.104426>
- Stroh, D. P. (2015). *Systems thinking for social change: A practical guide to solving complex problems, avoiding unintended consequences, and achieving lasting results*. Chelsea Green Publishing.
- Tomaszewska, J. (2020). Polish Transition towards Circular Economy: Materials Management and Implications for the Construction Sector. *Materials*, 13(22), 5228. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13225228>

- Traeber-Burdin, S., & Varga, M. (2022). Dealing with complex situations: Towards a framework of understanding problems. *2022 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, 1431–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SMC53654.2022.9945102>
- Vargas Falla, A. M., Brink, E., & Boyd, E. (2024). Quiet resistance speaks: A global literature review of the politics of popular resistance to climate adaptation interventions. *World Development*, 177, 106530. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2023.106530>
- Webb, D. C., Boswinkel, N., & Dekker, T. (2008). *Beneath the Tip of the Iceberg: Using Representations to Support Student Understanding*. <https://doi.org/10.5951/MTMS.14.2.0110>
- Weiner, E. S. (2010). *Market Dreams: Gender, Class, and Capitalism in the Czech Republic*. University of Michigan Press.
- Westenskow, A., Moyer-Packenham, P., & Child, B. (2017). An Iceberg Model for Improving Mathematical Understanding and Mindset or Disposition: An Individualized Summer Intervention Program. *Journal of Education*, 197(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002205741719700102>
- Williams, T. G., Bürgi, M., Debonne, N., Diogo, V., Helfenstein, J., Levers, C., Mohr, F., Stratton, A. E., & Verburg, P. H. (2024). Mapping lock-ins and enabling environments for agri-food sustainability transitions in Europe. *Sustainability Science*, 19(4), 1221–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01480-y>
- Woźniak, J., & Pactwa, K. (2019). Possibilities for using mine waters in the context of the construction of heat energy clusters in Poland. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 9(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-019-0195-2>
- Zagata, L., Hrabák, J., & Lošťák, M. (2020). Post-socialist transition as a driving force of the sustainable agriculture: A case study from the Czech Republic. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 44(2), 238–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21683565.2019.1585400>
- Zielińska-Szczepkowska, J., Jaszczak, A., & Žukovskis, J. (2021). Overcoming Socio-Economic Problems in Crisis Areas through Revitalization of Cittaslow Towns. Evidence from North-East Poland. *Sustainability*, 13(14), 7984. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147984>
- Żołądek, M., Kafetzis, A., Figaj, R., & Panopoulos, K. (2022). Energy-Economic Assessment of Islanded Microgrid with Wind Turbine, Photovoltaic Field, Wood Gasifier, Battery, and Hydrogen Energy Storage. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12470. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912470>
- Zubala, T. (2022). Effect of transport infrastructure development on selected components of the environment of inner-city river valley and the possibility of its revitalization (Lublin, Poland). *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(29), 44862–44873. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-18964-y>

Żuk, Piotr, & Żuk, Paweł. (2024). Ecology for the rich? Class aspects of the green transition and the threat of right-wing populism as a reaction to its costs in Poland. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 20(1), 2351231. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2024.2351231>